

Innovative strategies for accelerating carbonation: unraveling the catalytic potential of Metal-Organic Frameworks

Teodora Ilić^{1*}, Encarnación Ruiz-Agudo¹, and Carlos Rodriguez-Navarro¹

¹University of Granada, Faculty of Science, Department of Mineralogy and Petrology, Granada, 18071, Spain

Abstract. Innovative lime-based plaster and render formulations integrating metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) as additives were explored to advance carbon neutrality in lime production and application. Inspired by the catalytic efficiency of natural carbonic anhydrase, MOFs' potential to enhance carbonation in lime water and pastes was investigated. Four MOF groups—UiO-66/UiO-66(NH₂), ZIF-L, ZIF-EC-1, and MOF-808—were synthesized to facilitate CO₂ sequestration via atmospheric carbonation curing. Micro-Raman spectroscopy, optical microscopy, and ion-selective electrode titration were used to evaluate MOFs' influence on carbonation kinetics, calcium carbonate nucleation, and phase evolution in lime water. The degree of carbonation in the lime pastes with MOF additives was examined over three months. Results indicated enhanced kinetics of amorphous calcium carbonate formation and its transformation into calcite with MOFs. This research underscores MOFs' catalytic potential in lime carbonation, with significant implications for reducing CO₂ emissions in the lime industry.

Introduction

To enhance carbon neutrality in lime-based materials, this study aims to evaluate the potential of specific additives to accelerate the carbonation process. Previous research [1] has shown that enzymes, such as carbonic anhydrase, can catalyze the reaction between lime and carbon dioxide, thereby increasing the rate of calcium carbonate crystallization. However, carbonic anhydrase has limitations, including instability in alkaline conditions and high costs.

Therefore, this study explores novel biomimetic compounds with structures similar to carbonic anhydrase to promote carbonation. Several metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) were selected for investigation: UiO-66/UiO-66-NH₂, ZIF-L, ZIF-EC-1, and four types of MOF-808. MOFs and ZIFs are porous materials composed of metal ions or clusters bonded to organic ligands. The incorporation of MOFs or ZIFs in lime-based materials is relatively unexplored [2]. This study uses various techniques to investigate their impact on the carbonation kinetics of lime plasters.

Experiments and results

Two primary sets of tests were conducted: one in lime water (calcium hydroxide solution) and another in lime paste to evaluate the carbonation reaction over time. Pure hydrated lime from Lhoist Group was used as a reference. MOFs were added to the saturated calcium hydroxide solution and initially analyzed using micro-Raman spectroscopy. The evolution of particles, from amorphous calcium carbonate (ACC) to calcite, was tracked. After the water droplets evaporated, the residual crystals were further analyzed with Raman spectroscopy.

* Corresponding author: teodora@go.ugr.es

For the carbonation tests, small cube samples containing lime and 1 ppm, or 10 ppm of the selected MOFs were cast and then analyzed over a period of three months. Analysis of the materials is ongoing, with preliminary results available from TGA, XRD, and SEM. For brevity, this abstract includes a segment of the TGA study conducted over 14 days.

The incorporation of ZIF-EC-1 significantly accelerated the conversion of amorphous calcium carbonate to calcite on the droplet surface, with calcite crystals forming four times faster compared to the reference sample without the MOF (Fig. 1a). Conversely, ZIF-EC-1 did not perform as well in lime pastes, as evidenced by TGA results, which showed the fastest conversion to calcite with the addition of UiO-66 (Fig. 1b).

Fig. 1. a) Micro-Raman microscopy images of calcium lime-water droplets with ZIF-EC-1 after 10 minutes, showing the transformation of ACC particles to calcite crystals. b) Thermogram of lime paste samples with different MOF additives after 14 days of carbonation.

Fig. 2. Carbonation degree measured at 7, 10 and 14 days, based on TGA tests.

Preliminary TGA results over 14 days (Fig. 2) indicated that UiO-66 and ZIF-L were the most efficient additives. Sampling will be conducted at one, two and three months for further study.

Concluding remarks

The tests analyzed so far indicate that MOFs significantly impact the rate of calcite formation, suggesting their efficacy in accelerating the carbonation process in solution. In the lime-paste tests, UiO-66 and ZIF-L showed a significant increase in the degree of carbonation within the first 14 days. Further experiments are ongoing to understand the underlying mechanisms and to evaluate the effects of increased MOF concentrations. These findings highlight the potential and novelty of using MOFs in lime-based materials.

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References

1. Ö. Cizer et al. Kinetic effect of carbonic anhydrase enzyme on the carbonation reaction of lime mortar. *Int. J of Arch Heritage*, 2018, No. 5, p. 779-789.
2. M. M. Hulagabali et al. Synthesis, Characterization, and Application of ZIF-67 Metal-Organic Framework to Enhance the Microstructure and Compressive Strength of Cement Composite, *J of Mat in Civil Eng*, 35(5).